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Stabilisation of Molybdenyl Cation in the Environment of Halide Ions and Synthesis of New Salts

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THE chemistry of quinquevalent molybdenum has been investigated by Saha and his coworkers¹⁻⁴ through the isolation and study of various salt type compounds $RH_2[MoOX_5]$ and $RH[MoOX_4]$ (where R is organic base, X=Cl and Br). The comparable basic properties of the 2-picolyamine (α -pic) with pyridine has been established through the isolation of similar salts (α -pic.H) $[MoOCl_4]$ and (α -pic.H₂) $[MoOBr_5]$ by the present authors. The present communication deals with attempts to establish the good donating activity of the ligand 2-picolyamine having the $[-N-C-C-N-]$ type of linkage through the isolation and study of the salts. It was experienced earlier that due to comparatively greater basicity of the pyridine dehydrohalogenation leading to the formation of the non-electrolyte $[MoOX_5.py_2]$ could not be possible directly from either $PyH[MoOBr_4]$ or $(PyH_2)[MoOX_5]$. Here also direct dehydrohalogenation and hydrolysis of the salts (α -pic.H) $[MoOCl_4]$ and (α -pic.H₂) $[MoOBr_5]$ were carried out but no pure compounds could be isolated.

The salts have been characterised by analytical data and other physico-chemical investigations.

Experimental

All reagents used were of A. R. grade.

Analysis: Molybdenum and halogens were estimated¹⁻³ gravimetrically as MoO_3 and AgX respectively. Nitrogen was estimated by Dumas' method. Oxidation state of the metal was determined by ceric sulphate method.

Preparation:

2-Picolyaminium oxotetrachloro molybdate(V) (α -pic.H) $[MoOCl_4]$: A sample of about 2 g of molybdenum trioxide was dissolved in 10 ml of concentrated hydrochloric acid (12 N) with stirring. 2 ml hydroiodic acid were then added and gently boiled to drive off the liberated iodine. Minimum quantity of concentrated hydrochloric acid was added to the concentrated small mass when a bright green solution was obtained. 2 ml of 2-picolyamine dissolved in minimum quantity of concentrated

hydrochloric acid in cold were added to this solution and the mixture was again boiled. On cooling to room temperature light green crystalline solid began to separate. This was filtered in a sintered gooch crucible and dried in vacuum over solid KOH. Yield was about 5.7 g. Found: Mo, 26.34; Cl, 39.16; N, 6.90%. Calcd. for $C_8H_9N_3[MoOCl_4]$: Mo, 26.44; Cl, 39.06; N, 7.70%. Oxidation state of the metal was found to be 5.02.

2-Picolyaminium oxopentabromo molybdate(V), (α -pic.H₂) $[MoOBr_5]$: About 1 g of molybdenum trioxide was dissolved in 10 ml of hot 48% hydrobromic acid with stirring and concentrated to a pasty mass. To the small mass further 10 ml of conc. hydrobromic acid added and concentrated. The operation was repeated till a clear yellow solution of oxopentabromo molybdic(V) acid was obtained. 1 ml of 2-picolyamine acidified with hydrobromic acid was then added to this yellow solution with stirring and the mixture boiled. Golden yellow crystalline solid separated out on cooling to room temperature. It was filtered through sintered gooch crucible and dried in vacuum over solid KOH. Yield was about 3.5 g. Found: Mo, 14.87; Br, 62.4; N, 4.36%. Calcd. for $C_8H_{10}N_3[MoOBr_5]$: Mo, 15.40; Br, 64.3; N, 4.50%. Oxidation state of the metal was found to be 4.89.

Properties: Conductivity measurements of the salts (α -pic.H) $[MoOCl_4]$ and (α -pic.H₂) $[MoOBr_5]$ in aqueous medium show that they are extensively hydrolysed and ionised. The salts (μ_{eff} for α -pic.H $[MoOCl_4]$ = 1.69 B. M. at 28° and μ_{eff} for α -pic.H₂ $[MoOBr_5]$ = 1.58 B. M. at 28°) contain molybdenum in quinquevalent state. Infrared spectra of these compounds clearly show $\nu(Mo=O)$ frequency at 980-985 cm^{-1} .

TABLE I—ELECTRONIC SPECTRA

Compounds	λ_{max} in m μ	$\nu(cm^{-1} \times 10^{-3})$	Molar Extinction ϵ	Assignments
(α -pic.H) $[MoOCl_4]$	670	14.9	19	$^2B_2 \rightarrow ^2E(I)$
	417	23.9	35	$^2B_2 \rightarrow ^2B_1$
	354	28.2	590	$^2B_2 \rightarrow ^2E(II)$
	310	32.3	3630	$^2B_2 \rightarrow ^2B_2(I)$
	260	38.5	7400	$^2B_2 \rightarrow ^2B_2(II)$
	215	46.5	6620	$^2B_2 \rightarrow ^2E(III)$
(α -pic.H ₂) $[MoOBr_5]$	468	21.4	920	$^2B_2 \rightarrow ^2E(I)$
	415	24.1	5610	$^2B_2 \rightarrow ^2B_1$
	379	26.4	3000	$^2B_2 \rightarrow ^2E(II)$
	298	34.1	4070	$^2B_2 \rightarrow ^2B_2(I)$
	248	40.3	19450	$^2B_2 \rightarrow ^2E(III)$

Electronic spectra: The electronic spectra of the salts were recorded in "Varian Series" 634 UV

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Fig. 1. α -Picolyaminium oxotetrachloro molybdate(V)
 α -pic.H[MoOCl₄] in 12MHCl.

Fig. 2. α -Picolyaminium oxopenta bromomolybdate(V),
 α -pic.H₃[MoOBr₆] in 48% HBr.

spectrophotometer using AnalaR grade solvents. Electronic spectra of the chloro and bromo salts were taken in 12 M HCl and 48% HBr respectively. Results are tabulated in Table 1. The assignments are made on the basis of previous observations¹⁻³. The diagrammatic representation of the results are given in Figs. 1 and 2.

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**Dioxouranium(VI) Complexes with Tridentate
ONO Donor Schiff Bases Derived from
Benzoylhydrazide and Salicylaldehyde
or Substituted Salicylaldehydes**

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ALTHOUGH there has been considerable interest in the Schiff base complexes of first transition series metal ions^{1,2} little work has been reported on such complexes with higher transition series metal ions. As relatively few dioxouranium(VI) complexes with tridentate Schiff bases are known³, we report here the syntheses of dioxouranium(VI) complexes of the Schiff bases (I).

R=H, 5-Bromo, 5-Chloro, 5-Nitro, 5-Methoxy, 3-Methoxy, 3-Ethoxy, 3,5-Dichloro, 5,6-Benzo.

Experimental

Benzoylhydrazide was prepared according to published procedure⁴. The Schiff bases were prepared by following the method described elsewhere⁵.

General method of syntheses of the complexes: Uranylacetate dihydrate (0.84 g, 2 m mole) was dissolved in 10 ml of methanol. A methanolic solution of the Schiff base (2 m mole in 15 ml) was added to this and the mixture was refluxed for 3 hrs. The precipitate was filtered, washed with methanol and dried *in vacuo*. Yield=70%. U% and N% were determined by standard methods^{5,6}. Molecular weight, conductance, magnetic susceptibility, ir and electronic spectral data were recorded as usual⁷.